

Draft FGD Guide for Staff Nurses and Pediatric Residents
FOCUS GROUP DIRECTIONS

Hello, my name is _____ and I will be facilitating this focus group with you. This is _____ who will take notes during our discussion. This focus group will take approximately 1.5 hours.

The reason for conducting this focus group today is to hear about your thoughts, opinions, and observations about providing care to babies in the SNCU. I will be asking specifically about the barriers and facilitators to providing the best care for babies, including questions about equipment in the SNCU.

With your permission I would like to audio record the discussion; however, no names or other identifying information will be used during the focus group. Each participant will be given a number. To facilitate accurate attribution of responses to specific participants, I will ask you to state your participant number before speaking. Please refrain from addressing each other by name.

Before we begin the focus group, I want to provide some information about how it will be conducted. I will start the focus group by asking the first question and then facilitate from there as I incorporate the rest of the questions I have into the discussion. I would like you to do the majority of the talking and for everyone to participate to the best of their ability and comfort. There are also no right or wrong answers to any of the questions asked.

Do you have any questions before I start? YES NO

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

FGD Participant Number	Gender	Age
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		

Facilitator's name: _____
Notetaker's name: _____
Date: Start time: _____ End time: _____ Duration: _____ (min)

Barriers to optimal care: Equipment

I would like to ask you a series of questions regarding the challenges or barriers to providing the best care to babies in the SNCU. I would like to start with questions about the equipment used in the SNCU.

- 1) What equipment or accessories do you use the most? What pieces of equipment are the most useful? Why? What pieces of equipment are the least useful? Why? Do you have enough equipment to provide optimal care?
- 2) Which pieces of equipment or accessories are easier to use? Which ones are the most difficult? Why?
- 3) Do you have access to equipment user manuals? If yes, are they easy to understand and follow?
- 4) What are the most important equipment functions? How well does your current equipment perform these functions? What factors affect equipment function? Probe for electrical current problems.
- 5) What spare parts do you need to use the equipment properly? (Ask about attachments, accessories and consumables). Which ones are you missing? Why?
- 6) Do you share the equipment with other units? If so, with which units? How does sharing affect your ability to provide optimal care?
- 7) Do you share the equipment among babies simultaneously, for example placing more than 1 baby in a warmer at a time? If so, how often and why?
- 8) How do you monitor the performance of the equipment? How often do you experience problems with the equipment? Which ones are the most troublesome? Who is responsible for getting equipment repaired?
- 9) How often is the equipment cleaned? Who does that?
- 10) Which equipment is easier to clean? Which equipment is the most difficult to clean? Why?
- 11) What equipment do you trust the most? Why? The least? Why? Have these been on-going problems?
- 12) What types of equipment do you have that you do not use? Why not?
- 13) How many pieces of equipment do you have now in the SNCU that are broken or not functioning properly?
- 14) What needs to be done to address these barriers?

Barriers at the Staff Level:

Now, I would like to ask you a series of questions regarding the barriers to providing the best care to babies at the staff level.

- 15) Are the staffing levels adequate to cover the needs? Why or why not?
- 16) Are there standard operating procedures in the SNCU? Are these available to staff? Are you able to follow these? How useful are they? How often do you refer to them?
- 17) Can you tell me about staff turnover?
- 18) How are SNCU staff trained on the equipment? How often does training happen? Who does it?

- 19) Who is responsible for overseeing equipment maintenance issues? Who is responsible for requesting repairs?
- 20) Are there certain times of the day when you experience the most difficulties providing optimal care for babies? Why? How about certain times of the week? Month? Year?
- 21) Could you tell me about any challenges to working in the physical work space?
- 22) What needs to be done to address these?

Barriers at the Systems Level:

Now, I would like to ask you a series of questions about barriers to providing the best care at the systems level.

- 23) How do hospital policies affect your ability to provide optimal care for babies? Are there some policies you would like to see amended? In what ways?
- 24) What are some of the factors that make it difficult to prevent the spread of infection in the SNCU?
- 25) How long are nurses typically on a shift? How do staff handover from one shift to another? Are there any procedures they go through with regard to clinical care? Equipment use and monitoring? Do shift changes affect care for babies? In what ways?
- 26) Who is responsible for monitoring the function of the equipment? Whether equipment needs repair or maintenance? What happens when a piece of equipment breaks down? Do you have spare pieces of equipment or spare parts? Who repairs and maintains equipment?
- 27) What is your opinion of the service you receive? On average, how quickly are equipment failures addressed? How many days does it take for the equipment to be fully repaired? Why?
- 28) Is there a process for you to request new or different equipment?
- 29) What needs to be done to address these barriers?
- 30) Of the challenges you mentioned, what are the most important to providing optimal care?
- 31) Of the barriers you mentioned, what are the most important challenges to providing optimal care? Would you change any of the ranking we did at the beginning of the discussion?

Facilitators to optimal care

Now I would like to ask you a few questions about what helps you provide the best care to babies in the SNCU.

- 32) What is working well in terms of providing optimal care to babies in SNCUs?
 - a. **At the equipment level**
 - i. Design (user-friendliness, ease of maintenance)
 - ii. Manuals and trainings (SOPs)
 - b. **At the staff level**
 - i. Clinical expertise (level of knowledge and capacity)
 - ii. Training
 - iii. Numbers (inventory v. occupancy appropriate)

- iv. Efficiencies (time management, resources, work flows)
- c. **At the systems level** (how the SNCU is operated, decision-making regarding procurement, repair and maintenance of equipment, etc.)

Needs and gaps in optimal care

Now I would like to ask you a few questions about the needs and gaps in providing the best care to babies in the SNCU.

- 33) What more do you need in terms of equipment to be able to provide the best care to babies in SNCUs?
 - a. What equipment needs to be improved? What functions on the equipment need to be improved? What accessories? What spare parts?
 - b. What equipment functions do you need that you do not currently have? How about accessories? Spare parts? Consumables?
 - c. What functions of your existing equipment do you have that you do not use? Why? What accessories do you have but don't use. Why?
 - d. When your equipment breaks down, what do you do?
 - e. Are there spare parts available for the equipment?

Needs and gaps in optimal care (Staffing)

- 34) What more needs to be done at the level of staffing to provide the best care for babies in the SNCUs?
 - a. What additional training do staff need? Probe for clinical decision-making, equipment use, time management, work flow

Needs and gaps in optimal care (Systems)

- 35) What are the gaps or needs at the systems level to enable you to provide the best care to babies in the SNCUs?
 - a. What changes would enable you to provide the best care to babies in the SNCU?
 - b. What could be done to improve efficiencies in SNCU operations? Probe for clinical staff management, time management, capacity to address faulty equipment, response times for repair or replacement of equipment.

Recommendations to improve care for babies in the SNCUs

- 36) What recommendations do you have for improving care for babies in your SNCU?
- 37) Do you have anything else you would like to add?

Thank you for your participation!